

Non-Conformance in the Examination and Assessment of Joint Memorandum Circular: Basis for Enhanced Monitoring and Inspection Tools for Maritime Programs in the Philippines

Marvin P. Japitana, PhD

*Graduate Studies, John B. Lacson Foundation Maritime University,
Molo, Iloilo City, Philippines*

Abstract

This study examined the conformance of Maritime Higher Education Institutions (MHEIs) with Key Area IV (Examination and Assessment) of the Joint CHED-MARINA Memorandum Circular (JCMMC). It focuses on the congruency of the results of respondent auditors who are experienced in the inspection and audit to the noted non-conformance report identified by the monitoring team using the existing Outcomes-based Monitoring Instrument (OBMI). The existing methodologies frequently exhibit subjectivity, vagueness and incongruent findings during inspection. The research evaluated the CHED-MARINA monitoring scheme and audit tools in relation to examination and assessment. An ex-post facto technique is employed based on document analysis and quantitative-descriptive for data analysis. Data were obtained from the monitoring report of 15 MHEIs nationwide and 25 auditor respondents' surveys. The results showed significant disparities and inconsistencies by auditors in the classification of observed findings across Section 16 provided in the current OBMI. The study recommended an enhanced monitoring instrument to address its notable gap by providing a standardized framework for objective and comprehensive memorandum circular compliance verification. This tool will allow regulatory bodies to evaluate and deploy suggested monitoring across critical domains to demonstrate the quality and uniformity of assessment methods. The implications of the study are substantial, indicating that the recommended enhanced OBMI can call for a more robust theoretical framework for evaluating compliance that promotes reliability and transparency of audit results grounded in an established quality standards system. Consequently, training for auditors is crucial through the calibration of inspection ethics to improve reliability and transparency of results.

Keywords: *Maritime Education, Outcomes-based Monitoring Tool, Non-conformance, Auditors, Examination and Assessment.*

Suggested citation: Japitana, M.P. (2025). Non-Conformance in the Examination and Assessment of Joint Memorandum Circular: Basis for Enhanced Monitoring and Inspection Tools for Maritime Programs in the Philippines. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 3(5), 32-47. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2025.3(5).03

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

The Philippines is an archipelagic nation with the highest global seafarer employment rate and a rich maritime legacy. It supports the fourth item in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) set by the International Maritime Organization (IMO). This goal calls for high-quality education that fosters equitable and inclusive academic opportunities, alongside lifelong learning initiatives. Auditors from the Independent Evaluation (IE) and European Maritime Safety Agency (EMSA) conduct assessment of the quality standards system (QSS) of MHEIs utilizing structured audit tools, such as the Outcomes-based Monitoring Instrument (OBMI). The process is designed to ensure thorough compliance with the standards of maritime education and training set forth in the International Convention on Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW) 1978, as amended. The OBMI, employed collaboratively by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) and the Maritime Industry Authority (MARINA), reinforces 83 Maritime Higher Education Institutions (MHEI) in fulfilling the criteria for accreditation, monitoring, and surveillance audits outlined in the Convention and the Joint CHED-MARINA Memorandum Circular (JCMCC) series of 2022.

Nonconformities (NC) identified in the Monitoring of Findings and Corrective Action Report (MFCAR) of MHEIs were useful in pinpointing the most susceptible critical area that substantially impacts the quality of education in the country. It aimed for congruence in classifying audit findings utilizing the OBMI based on the viewpoints of the participants from the provided CHED-MARINA MFCARs. Conversely, the national evaluators must communicate that the audit assessed the quality of the inspection tools as eliminating errors and biases in judgment. Notwithstanding rigorous oversight of all critical domains, the uncertainty and vagueness of the auditor's interpretation continue to be a problem for achieving consistency in NC. This circumstance ultimately jeopardizes the credibility of the audit. NC often has a stigma of substandard performance and poor-quality delivery, which is typically linked with a negative blame culture (Ford et al., 2023).

The result of the reports on the issued findings depicts the discombobulation of quality assurance and a deficient academic framework for maritime education and training. Non-compliance with international standards, safety protocols, and curriculum requirements can lead to inadequately prepared seafarers and increased risks (Nhleko, 2023). One of the causes of incongruence was the lack of indicator's specificity. Lack of organized indicators leads to subjective interpretation and erratic reports. The inconsistency of the noted findings, evidenced by disparity in the MFCAR, affects the effectiveness of maritime instructions and assessments for students. The implementation of a Quality Management System (QMS) serves as a comprehensive framework for educational institutions, enabling them to establish standardized processes and quality procedures that promote consistent practices within their systems (Pabutawa, 2023).

Consequently, various discrepancies in the classification of NCs based on their item placement in the indicators considerably reflect the gaps. This circumstance reveals an absence of uniform interpretation and compliance with the current guidelines. This

scenario results in a peculiar and chaotic inspection process, subsequently yielding erroneous reports and tensile analyses.

The objective of the study was to ascertain how monitoring teams and responding inspectors utilize the existing OBMI to categorize non-conformance reports and to evaluate the similarity of their assessments. To mitigate the pressing issues of inconsistencies of reports, it requires an integrated and comprehensive strategy that involves stakeholders from government, industry, and academia to ensure the Philippines remains a leading supplier of highly qualified and skilled maritime professionals on the world stage (Chibana, 2024). The integration will help researcher improve tools for inspection and monitoring to comply with the minimum academic requirements set by STCW 1978, as amended.

This study examined the alignment between the audit results of the monitoring team and assessed the consistency of their interpretations. Additionally, it aimed to establish a basis for improving the existing OBMI to ensure more reliable, objective, and transparent audit outcomes.

Methodology

This study used ex-post facto (causal-comparative research) to see if the national report in the MFCAR matched what the respondent auditors thought in terms of specificity, comprehensiveness, and fairness. It was also used to study cause-and-effect relationships after the inspection and audit results were sent to the Commission and Administration. According to Black (1999), an ex-post facto study is a type of study where researchers have limited control over the independent variable because it is usually a life event or a life experience of the participant that cannot be manipulated, unlike in studies with an experimental design.

The study was also supported by quantitative-descriptive methods, which were employed to collect data to test hypotheses or answer questions concerning the current status of the subjects (Gay, 2002). Descriptive type of research explains and interprets relationships that exist, the perceptions of the participants, the present conditions of processes, and the effects that are evident or trends that are developing (Best and Kahn, 1998). In this study, a descriptive approach was used to see how well the monitoring team's reports matched the opinions of the auditors using the current OBMI.

Respondents were 25 experienced auditors from both the regulatory bodies and MHEIs involved in the external and internal audits. The niche and emergent nature of maritime audits, which is characterized by a scarcity of qualified auditors in the national and institutional sectors, was the reason for the limited number of participants. The representation remains valid and meaningful despite the modest sample size, as the selected participants have specialized backgrounds and direct experience that are pertinent to the study's objectives. Their insights reflect the realities of audits and inspections within the MHEIs. To ensure relevance and depth, purposive sampling was employed to gather responses from the filled-out categorization of the 14 noted NCs based on the existing indicators of the OBMI during monitoring inspections nationwide.

This study adopted the current OBMI tools of the JCMCC in conjunction with survey instruments consisting of two components found in Section A – Demographic Profiles and Section B – Statements of categorized NC derived from prevalent NC in the key

areas of examination and assessment, along with respondents' responses on the classification of noted findings according to the established indicators of the OBMI sections.

Respondents were apprised of the study's objectives, methodologies, and any risks and advantages. Respondents have the opportunity to pose questions and withdraw from the study at any moment. All collected data was maintained in confidentiality. The identities of respondents were safeguarded, and the data was anonymized before analysis. All data was securely stored and accessed exclusively by authorized personnel. The research findings were articulated, clearly, and potential biases or limitations were acknowledged. The MFCARs in this study were restricted solely to the monitoring activities in which the researcher participated.

The researcher utilized both an online survey via electronic documents and physical survey instruments distributed to CHED and MARINA auditors engaged in nationwide monitoring inspections, along with MHEIs' managerial officers and technical auditors involved in its internal audit activities. The collection of information is in conformance with the salient provisions under Republic Act 10173, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

The following analyses were observed in the collection of data: (1) document analysis on how to determine the most prevalent types of NC, and (2) quantitative data analysis to derive the mean and frequency.

The responses were carefully scrutinized, evaluated, and analyzed through the *Mean* with interpretation on the Likert scale as follows: *Congruent*, *Incongruent*, and *Not Relevant*, respectively, while for the *Frequency*, it focuses on the most options chosen, which were considered to compare and match on the national reports. The analyzed data shed light and derived a recommendation to enhance the existing OBMI on Annex E-4 of JCMMC 03, series of 2022.

Results

Most Prevalent Types of Non-Conformity among MHEIs

This section presents the study's findings, highlighting four significant themes that emerged from the actual nonconformities of the schools relative to the different key areas. The first objective was to identify the most prevalent types of NC among MHEIs as outlined in the Joint CHED-MARINA Memoranda Circulars. Secondly, analyze how the monitoring team and the respondent auditors categorize a non-conformance report using the Outcomes-based Monitoring Instrument (OBMI). Thirdly, evaluate the congruency between the monitoring team's and the respondent auditors' categorization of a non-conformance (NC) report using the Outcomes-based Monitoring Instrument (OBMI); and lastly, to recommend an enhanced monitoring and inspection tools that address and improve the congruency of audit reports produced by different auditors.

Table 1 shows that the most frequent issues found in MHEIs were in Key Area IV (Examination and Assessment), with 34 problems out of 179 identified by the monitoring team from 15 inspected MHEIs using the current OBMI of the JCMMC.

Table 1. Summary of NCs According to Its Key Area of MHEIs in the Region

SCHOOL		KEY AREA									TOTAL NCs
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	
LUZON	A	4	2	-	4	1	3	-	-	-	14
	B	1	2	1	2	1	5	1	-	-	13
	C	1	1	-	3	-	2	-	-	-	7
	D	-	-	1	1	-	2	-	-	-	4
	E	1	1	-	2	3	1	-	-	-	8
VISAYAS	F	2	1	2	3	4	2	1	1	-	16
	G	3	1	4	-	-	1	2	1	-	12
	H	2	3	1	2	2	-	-	1	-	11
	I	2	-	1	2	1	-	1	1	-	8
	J	-	1	-	1	1	1	-	1	-	5
MINDANAO	K	4	1	4	3	2	-	-	-	-	14
	L	3	3	5	3	1	7	1	1	-	24
	M	4	2	2	2	1	3	2	1	1	18
	N	1	-	1	4	4	2	-	1	-	13
	O	3	1	1	2	-	1	-	2	-	10
TOTAL NCs		31	19	23	34	21	32	8	10	1	179

Key Area: I – Program and Course Design, Review and Approval; II – Required Resources; III – Standards, Teaching Methods and Media of Delivery; IV – Examination and Assessment System; V – Facilities and Equipment for Education and Training; VI – Onboard Training; VII – Student Admission and Retention; VIII – Quality Standards System; IX – Research and Extension. NC - Nonconformance

Table 2. Placement of Total NCs According to Sections and OBMI Indicators of JCMMC

	Title of Section							Total (NCs)
	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	
No. of indicators	4	3	2	2	2	3	4	
Non-conformity (NC)	25	1	0	1	1	5	1	34

Table 2 presented the 34 NCs classified according to their placement in the relevant sections outlined in Article VII, as noted in the reports submitted to the Commission and Administration. The figure below is classified based on its commonalities across sections.

It showed the number of NCs in each section of Key Area IV. As a result, Section 16, “The MHEI shall design and develop, review and verify, validate and approve their theoretical and practical assessment tools for all Course Outcomes defined in the course specifications”, had the most NCs, totaling 25.

Comparison of the Category of Non-conformities by Indicators

The analysis was conducted based on its theme and classified according to commonalities of the findings and placed under 4 indicators outlined in Section 16 of the current OBMI of JCMMC. The subsequent descriptions are organized according to the specified indicators:

- A. Existing policy and procedure on the design and development, review and verification, validation process and approval for theoretical and practical assessment tools for

all Course Outcomes.

B. Records of the development, review, verification and validation of the theoretical and practical assessment tools and members comprising the development of theoretical and practical assessment tools.

C. Records of implementation of the policy and procedure on the design and development, review and verification, validation process and approval for theoretical and practical assessment tools for all Course Outcomes as to accomplished validation form for all course outcomes.

D. Records of implementation of the policy and procedure on the design and development, review and verification, validation process and approval for theoretical and practical assessment tools for all Course Outcomes as to administered/ marked theoretical and practical assessment tools for all course outcomes per individual student/ learner.

In general, data in Table 3 showed that the indicators in both “Survey Category”, which presented the results of analysis from the gathered responses of this study while “Inspection Category” were the noted reports depicted in the MFCARs. Table 3 delineated NCs categorized according to thematic segregation by indicators, resulting in a total of 14 common NCs out of 25.

Table 3. Thematic Segregation of NCs to Its Indicator under Section 16 by the Monitoring Team and the Respondent Auditors

NC	Description	Survey Category	Inspection Category	Mean	Interpretation
1	Time allocation, thinking order skills and item placement do not align with the TOS and there are missing corresponding test items aligned to its table of specifications (TOS)	A	C	2.44	Incongruent
2	Learning outcomes for demonstration were not programmed on a specific simulator for actual performance	D	C	2.60	Incongruent
3	No corresponding performance criteria and standards found in the practical assessment tools	D	C	2.64	Incongruent
4	The stated learning outcome is not aligned with the indicated competence, KUPs and syllabus	A	C	2.28	Incongruent
5	No scoring tools (e.g. rubrics, checklist and rating) to measure the performance of the students if pass or fail	C	C	2.68	Congruent
6	No assessment tools or scenarios presented for assessment. Moreso, with the oral, written and practical aspect in the onboard training (OBT) assessment	B or D	D	2.84	Congruent
7	No document or assessment tool presented to substantiate the grading of the student who are assessed individually	C or D	C	3.04	Congruent
8	No explicit provisions for grading system of pure laboratory in consonance with Section 16 of Article VII and Section 40 of Article X	A	A	2.76	Congruent

9	No assessment plan/guide provided for different examination terms and how the practical assessment can be done or performed	A	C	2.52	Incongruent
10	No retention of records of assessment tools and its results within 3 years	B	C	2.48	Incongruent
11	It was noted that the assessment tools for the theoretical component in general education courses did not comply with the policy particularly item analysis	A	B	2.24	Incongruent
12	Specific number of practical assessment tools presented were not able to undergo the review and validation using its enrolled form	B or C	A	2.48	Incongruent
13	There are missing course outcomes in the design for assessment	C	D	2.64	Incongruent
14	No records presented for the Table of Outcomes Assessment (TOA) relative to Annex G	C	C	2.72	Congruent

Congruency of Non-Conformance with MFCARs

Extracted from data shown in Table 3, out of 14 nonconformances noted by the monitoring team, there were 5 NCs that matched (NC5, NC6, NC7, NC8, and NC14), and the rest were not congruent to MFCARs based on being the most responded-to options in the survey.

Enhanced Outcomes-based Monitoring Instrument

The improved audit tool was established by including the salient items that are frequently scrutinized and noted as findings during inspection. Appendix A presented the “*Enhanced Monitoring and Inspection Tool for Key Area IV – Annex E-4*” and Appendix B showed the “*Proposed Summary of all Key Areas in its Conformity Level*”. This upgraded design was a recommended instrument to be utilized during future accreditation, monitoring, inspection, evaluation and surveillance of MHEIs relative to their conformance to the JCMMCs.

Discussion

The analysis revealed that Key Area IV (Examination and Assessment) of the JCMMC 01 series of 2022 exhibited 34 out of 179 non-conformities, the highest count among the nine Key Areas. Key Area IV of Article VII consists of seven sections (Sections 16 to 22) and Section 16 earned 25 out of 34 NCs. Section 16 outlines the processes involved in the design, development, review, verification, validation, and approval of theoretical and practical assessment tools for all course outcomes, which is significant in gauging the readiness of the students to work onboard a ship. It encapsulates systematic challenges in evaluating their competencies outlined in the Seafarers’ Training, Certification, and Watchkeeping (STCW) Code in relation to assessment designs. Effective design requires a clear understanding of what is to be assessed, how it will be assessed, and how the resulting data will be used to improve teaching and learning (Pellegrino et al., 2022).

Table 4. Scale Measure in Identifying Relevant Congruence

Scale	Description	Interpretation
2.67 – 4.00	Congruent	Results of both survey and inspections are consistent with each other and aligns with expectations
1.34 – 2.66	Incongruent	Results of the survey vary from what has been previously observed or expected
Less than 1.34	Not relevant	Both results of the survey and inspections are not meaningful nor related with the objectives

The monitoring teams from the regulatory agencies categorized the identified most common 14 out of 25 non-conformances into groups according to the four established indicators (A-D). Table 3 presents the interpretations of the NC categories by 25 respondent auditors, highlighting the most frequently selected options. NC1 has 8 for option A; NC2 has 8 for option D; NC3 has 9 for option D; NC4 has 10 for option A; NC5 has 9 for option C; NC6 has 6 for both options B and D; NC7 has 9 for both options C and D; NC8 has 7 for option A; NC9 has 7 for option A; NC10 has 7 for option B; NC11 has 9 for option A; NC12 has 8 for both options B and C; NC13 has 9 for option C; NC14 has 7 for option C, respectively.

Based on Table 4, the Monitoring Team’s MFCARs indicated only 5 NCs (5 [2.68], 6 [2.84], 7 [3.04], 8 [2.76], and 14 [2.72]) match with the results of responses to be congruent bolstering results of both survey and inspection to be consistent with each other and aligns with expectations. Additionally, the common indicators with disparity among the congruence include the collection and preservation of evidence indicating that the development and approval of assessment tools adhered to the established policies and procedures of the Quality Standards System of MHEIs. A quality management system is an essential and mandatory instrument for MHEIs. The design and development of maritime assessment tools benefit from a systematic approach to quality control (Karcher et al., 2023). It was also seconded by Hebbar et al. (2020), where knowledge and skills are the results of well-organized study processes and training.

Many MHEIs have poor safekeeping of students’ assessment records, which is essential to determine that all competences were performed and satisfactorily met. Consequently, each institution is required to furnish evidence of implementation through recordkeeping. Documentary evidence from the three-year period must be accessible for compliance verification during the audit.

Nonconformities can be issued without proof that a student was assessed on particular elements found in the Knowledge, Understanding and Proficiency (KUP) of a standard of competence in the STCW tables. One challenging factor is the design and development of the assessment tools that must adhere to the quality process of review and approval which has the most prevalent deficiencies in the study. The overall aim is to investigate the validity and reliability of an assessment tool (Ernstsen & Nazir, 2020). Reliability is the consistency across time, items and researches while validity refers to the accuracy of measure with assessment construction, criterion, time and content. Both are needed to the successful implementation of quality assessment of outcomes.

Further, the 5 congruent NCs, while 9 NCs remain incongruent. Evidently, only one-third of common non-conformities align with the submitted MFCAR, depicting an

alarming situations due to disorganized OBMI. Congruence of the noted findings demonstrates the degree of uniformity and reliability, highlights consistent results, and supports effective strategies for improving maritime education, especially in maintaining student competence. Consistency ensures that similar instances of non-compliance or issues are treated uniformly across different audits (Jounila et al., 2017). However, the rest is the result of varied interpretation and improper internalization of the findings by the national auditors.

The proposed enhanced OBMI (Appendices A and B) is grounded in analytical results and aims to create a more effective monitoring and inspection tool that identifies specific areas requiring rigid scrutiny. The institution can utilize appropriate inspection tools to guarantee that all students engage in authentic learning and assessment which may acquire diverse shipboard management skills.

Conclusion

The study revealed prevalent noted deficiencies in the key area of examinations and assessments as detailed in Section 16 particularly regarding the design and testing of evaluation tools. This limns the graduates were unable to effectively address all the required outcomes set by the JCMMC, which is crucial in enhancing students' competencies and ensuring that all graduates adhere to the highest quality standards. This indicates that the institutions' standard system failed to satisfy the necessary quality standards and may poorly deploy inadequately trained seafarers to merchant vessels.

The substantial discrepancy in NC categories between monitoring teams and responding auditors indicated that the monitoring instruments were insufficient in terms of clarity, detail, and consistency. This contradiction emerged due to poorly defined indicators, which permitted multiple interpretations and led to erroneous conclusions. The findings revealed that the primary sectors of the JCMMC were deficient in equitable and rigorous monitoring protocols. The evaluation of nonconformity among 15 MHEIs was not thoroughly conducted due to ambiguous indicators, which resulted in inconsistent findings and difficulties in interpreting OBMI.

Only one-third of the total noted findings were congruent with the participants' responses, which is notably alarming. The presence of uncalibrated audit tools and non-indoctrinated evaluators indicates a deficient culture of monitoring and inspection, resulting in incongruency of reports.

The research indicated that inspection and evaluation of compliance among MHEIs in their quality maritime education systems require an improved OBMI, incorporating clearly defined indicators, metrics, and criteria to facilitate objective and consistent assessment. In light of this, CHED and MARINA are encouraged to adopt the proposed enhanced Monitoring and Inspection Tool to streamline the inspection and monitoring reports, thus accurately reflecting the true value of conformity level of the school.

Acknowledgement

I wish to convey my profound gratitude to Dr. Geneva M. Eler, Dean of the Graduate School of JBLFMU, together with the academics and colleagues, for their steadfast

support of our campaign. I extend my gratitude to Mr. Ralph C. Malacad for his expertise in statistical brainstorming and express my sincere appreciation to all my CHED technical evaluators, the MARINA monitoring team, and the MHEI internal auditors for their participation as respondents in this study. Thank you to the management of Philjade International, who provided me with support in various ways until this study was completed.

The success of my research is dedicated to my family, particularly to my mother, Mildred, who never complained during the late hours of work. To the OPSD colleagues, CHED Regional Office (CHEDRO) counterparts, and school management for permitting me to explore further into the audit results. I express my sincere gratitude to all my friends, whom I neglected to acknowledge, who definitely support my quest for change. Primarily, the supreme Almighty God bestows upon me wisdom and strength to embrace the problems of this study and instills in me a fervor to pursue its objectives with more determination. This would not have been possible without his supernatural presence in my heart and thoughts as an educator and seafarer.

Ethical Consideration

The study upheld ethical standards by ensuring voluntary participation, preceded by a brief orientation and informed consent embedded within the survey instrument. Respondents were required to meet age and cognitive criteria for valid engagement. Confidentiality of participant identities and related documents was strictly maintained throughout the research process. Participants retained the right to withdraw at any stage without consequence. Proper attribution of referenced scholarly works was observed, reinforcing academic integrity and ethical compliance in reporting.

Conflict of Interest

The researcher asserts that no conflict of interest exists in the execution and dissemination of this research. I have revealed all financial or personal relationships that may potentially affect the results of this study. The research was executed impartially, devoid of external financial sources or affiliations that could introduce bias into the results. The researcher asserts the dedication to preserving the integrity and transparency of the study process.

References

Best, J.W. and Kahn, J.V. (1998) *Research in Education*. 8th Edition, Butler University, Emeritus, University of Illinois, Chicago.

Black, T. R. (1999). *Doing quantitative research in the social sciences: An integrated approach to research design, measurement, and statistics*. Sage Publications.

Chibana, I. (2024). *Aligning Philippine seafarer education with EMSA directives: An approach to elevating global and local maritime standards*. Bangkok Research Center, *Institute of Developing Economies (IDE-JETRO)*, Chapter 3, page 69-92.

Demirel, E. (2020). *Maritime education and training in the digital era*. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(9), 4129–4142. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080939>

- Ernstsen, J., & Nazir, S. (2020). *Performance assessment in full-scale simulators – A case of maritime pilotage operations*. *Safety Science*, 129, 104775. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2020.104775>
- Ford, G., Gosling, J., & Naim, M. (2023). On quality and complexity: non-conformance failures, management perspectives and learning outcomes on a highways megaproject. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 40(10), 2539–2558. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijqrm-11-2022-0313>
- Gay, G. (2002). Preparing for Culturally-Responsive Teaching. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 53, 106-116. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0022487102053002003>
- Hebbar, N., Hebbar, N., Ouinas, D., & Bourada, M. (2020). *Numerical Modeling of Bending, Buckling and Vibration of Functionally Graded Beams by Using a Higher-Order Shear Deformation Theory*. 230-246, VL14. *Frattura ed Integrità Strutturale*. <https://doi.org/10.3221/IGF-ESIS.52.18>
- International Convention on *Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping for Seafarers (STCW) for Seafarers, 1978, as amended including Manila 2010 Amendments (2017 Edition)*.
- International Maritime Organization. (2020). *United Nations Sustainable Development Goal*. <https://sdgs.un.org/un-system-sdg-implementation/international-maritime-organization-imo-34611>
- JCMMC 01 Series of 2022, Policies, Standards and Guidelines for the Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation and Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering Programs. Annex A-L
- JCMMC 01 Series of 2023, Policies, Standards and Guidelines for the Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation and Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering Programs, Series of 2022, As Amended. Annex A-H
- JCMMC 03 Series of 2022, Guidelines and Procedures on Joint CHED-MARINA Monitoring of Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation and Bachelor of Science in Marine Engineering Programs, Series of 2022, Amended. Annex E(4)
- Jounila, H., Cajander, N., Reiman, A., Latva-Ranta, J., & Väyrynen, S. (2017). 1st Edition. *EQ assessment audit tool—consistency analysis of expert audits*. In *Prevention of Accidents at Work* (pp. 115–119). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315177571-16>
- Karcher, A., Arnold, D., & Kuhlenkötter, B. (2023). *Development of a Guideline Under Didactical Aspects for the Use of Immersive Virtual Learning Environments*. *Journal of Formative Design in Learning*, 7(2), 98–105. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41686-023-00085-5>
- Manuel, M. E. (2017). *Vocational and academic approaches to maritime education and training (MET): Trends, challenges, and opportunities*. *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs*, 16(3), 473–483. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13437-017-0130-3>
- Nhleko, Y. (2023). *Challenges in International Convention on the Standards of Training, Certification and Watchkeeping Compliance: A case study of the South African Maritime Education and Training System*. *South African Journal of Maritime Education and Training*, 2(1), 121–131. <https://doi.org/10.47348/sajmet/2023/i1a8>
- Pabutawa, E. L. P. (2024). *Investigating the outcomes-based education (OBE): A case study using the Philippine maritime education and training (MET) system*. World Maritime University.
- Pehlivan, D., & Cicek, K. (2021). *A knowledge-based model on quality management system compliance assessment for maritime higher education institutions*. *Quality in Higher Education*, 27(2), 239–263. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13538322.2021.1905654>

Pellegrino, J. W., DiBello, L. V., & Brophy, S. P. (2014). *The Science and Design of Assessment in Engineering Education*. In Cambridge Handbook of Engineering Education Research (pp. 571–598). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/cbo9781139013451.036>

Pettigrew, T. F. (1998). *Intergroup contact theory*. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 49(1), 65–85. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.49.1.65>

Republic Act 10173 (Data Privacy Act of 2012) – An Act Protecting Individual Personal Information in Information and Communications Systems in the Government and the Private Sector, Creating for this Purpose a National Privacy Commission and for other Purposes.

Santos, M., & De la Cruz, A. (2023). *Evaluating the effectiveness of monitoring instruments in maritime education*. *Philippine Journal of Maritime Studies*, 10(1), 112-127.

Appendix A

Enhanced Monitoring and Inspection Tool for Key Area IV – Annex E-4

ENHANCED MONITORING AND INSPECTION TOOL AUDIT OUTLINE AS FOR JCMMC 01, SERIES OF 2023 (KEY AREA 4 – EXAMINATION AND ASSESSMENT)				
RATING		INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS		
4	Evidence shows that the provision is very extensive and is functioning excellently.	100% Compliance – CONFORMANCE (CONF) 90% - 99% Compliance – OPPORTUNITY FOR IMPROVEMENT (OFI) 80% - 89% Compliance – OBSERVATION (OBS) 70% - 79% Compliance – MINOR NON-CONFORMANCE (mNC) Below 70% Compliance – MAJOR NON-CONFORMANCE (MNC) NOTE: Expected Points = total number of items × 4 (maximum rating); Average = Total earned points / Expected points; INT (refer to interpretation of finding, INT: CONF; OFI; OBS; mNC; MNC.)		
3	Evidence shows that the provision is adequate and functioning well.			
2	Evidence shows that the provision is limited but functioning well.			
1	Evidence shows that the provision is very limited and functioning poorly.			
0	There is no evidence and the provision is missing but necessary.			
TIME	KEY AREA & DESCRIPTION	OBJECTIVE EVIDENCE	RATING	AUDIT FINDING (Remarks)
	KEY AREA IV– Examination and Assessment System	1. Proof of established structured examination and assessment system (Annex E – JCMMC 01, s. 2023)		
		2. Records showing proof that the theoretical assessments tools have undergone the following elements: a. Design (spearhead by qualified assessor/s only and its approved forms)		
		b. review (designated person/s and its approved forms)		
		c. verification (designated person/s and its approved forms)		
		d. validated - time element or pilot testing (designated person/s and its approved forms)		
		e. validated – construct, content, face, criterion, and others elements (designated person/s and its approved forms)		
		f. approval – (designated person and its approved forms)		
		3. Records showing proof that the practical assessments tools have undergone the following elements: a. Design (spearhead by qualified assessor/s only and its approved forms)		

KEY AREA IV– Examination and Assessment System	b. review (designated person/s and its approved forms)		
	c. verification (designated person/s and its approved forms)		
	d. validated - time element or pilot testing (designated person/s and its approved forms)		
	e. validated – construct, content, face, criterion, and others elements (designated person/s and its approved forms)		
	f. approval – (designated person and its approved forms)		
	4. List of qualified Assessors and Invigilators duly approved by Department Head / Dean		
	5. Accomplished Practical Assessment Tools by students (including the deferred courses if there is any) within 3 years		
	6. QSS incorporates RETENTION PERIOD of records of Practical Exercises and Assessment		
	7. Accomplished Comprehensive Examinations prior to the conferment of degree as administered and conducted (Annex E – C6.6) covering STCW Competency Map and OBT, not included the Post Onboard Assessment		
	8. Summary of passers of the comprehensive examination prior to conferment of degree		
	9. Summary of records of student's completion of academic and other institutional requirements		
	10. Summary of passers of OBT assessments		
	11. Table of Specification (Annex E, Part D7) as per institutional policy, as applicable		
	12. Table of Outcomes Assessment – TOA (Annex E – E10.2 and Annex I)		
	13. Item analysis as basis of revising, removing, and retaining of assessment items (Annex E)		
14. Proof of action on the result of the item analysis (if removed – new test item aligned to the TOS, if revised – which one was revised and highlight the retained item)			
15. Approved grading system a. Pure lecture component			

		b. Lecture and Laboratory component				
		c. Pure laboratory component				
		16. Records of implementation of the approved grading system across all courses				
		17. Class records as proof showing compliance to the approved grading system				
AUDITOR		EXPECTED POINTS	116	EARNED POINTS		INT
				AVERAGE		

Overall Remarks:

Appendix B

Proposed Summary of all Key Areas in its Conformity Level

ENHANCED MONITORING AND INSPECTION SUMMARY

(KEY AREA 4 – EXAMINATION AND ASSESSMENT)

NO.	KEY AREA	SUM	EARNED	AVERAGE	VALUE
I	Program and Course Design, Review and Approval;				
II	Required Resources				
III	Standards, Teaching Methods and Media of Delivery				
IV	Examination and Assessment System	116			
V	Facilities and Equipment for Education and Training				
VI	Onboard Training				
VII	Student Admission and Retention				
VIII	Quality Standards System				
IX	Research and Extension				
	TOTAL	116	0		
		CONFORMITY LEVEL OF MHEI			

CHED-MARINA shall establish a multiplier of weights to determine the right value in each key area.

CONFORMITY LEVEL	
0.91 – 1.00	Excellent (E)
0.81 – 0.90	Satisfactory (S)
0.71 – 0.80	Average (A)
0.51 – 0.70	Poor (P)
0.21 – 0.50	Very Poor (VP)
0.00 – 0.20	Never Conformed (NC)

